

Economic assessment of alternative feed supplements to reduce methane emissions – a technical note

Shailesh Shrestha, Vera Eory, Klaus Glenk, Andrew Barnes

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Introduction

To achieve Scottish Government's aim to achieve NetZero emissions by 2045, farms are encouraged to adopt new technologies or alternative farm management strategies. Using methane inhibiting feed supplements to reduce enteric methane emission from cattle is a potential management measure to reduce emission from farms. There are many feed supplements ranging from natural food materials such as seaweed, essential oils and microbial proteins to natural/synthetic chemicals such as nitrates and 3NOP, which are listed as alternative feed supplements to reduce methane emission on livestock farms. There have been a number of studies in recent years to test efficacy of some of these feed supplements to reduce GHG emissions (Reynold et al., 2014; Hristov et al., 2015, 2020; Castro Montoya et al., 2015; Flockhart, 2017; van Wesemael et al., 2019, Melgar et al., 2020, 2021; Carrazco et al., 2020; Duthie et al., 2022; Wang, et al., 2023). These studies have shown that many feed supplements like seaweed and 3NOP are very effective in reducing enteric methane production (up to 90% reduction). Farmers' uptake of these feed supplements will depend on their availability, regulatory constraints or incentives, negative effects (both on animal health and environment) and ease of use. Crucially, the feed supplements need to be economically feasible and cost effective in reducing emissions for a widespread uptake by the farmers. This note presents a methodology to examine economic feasibility and cost effectiveness of feed supplements on livestock farms and preliminary results of two of the case study farming systems as example outputs. It is undertaken within the scope of SRUC-B3-1 – Ensuring positive behavioural change for farmers towards best practice for clean growth: economic and behavioural investigations with support of the Scottish Government, as part of the Environment, Natural Resources and Agriculture (ENRA) Strategic Research Programme 2022–2027.

Methods

We use a farm level optimising model to simulate farm net profits of the case study livestock farming systems. A comparative analysis is conducted on farm profits under different feed supplements to determine their impact on the farm economy. Changes in farm net profit compared to the reduction in farm methane emission is used to allow a cost benefit comparison of the feed supplements. It only includes the direct reduction in methane emission from animals. Any other

changes in emission due to feed change and other structural changes are not included in this study.

Farm data input

Farm level data used in this work is taken from the Scottish Farm Business Survey, FBS (SG, 2024). The survey contains physical and economic information of around 550 Scottish farms. The sampled farms are grouped in different farming systems based on enterprise. Four livestock farming systems (Dairy, Beef, Sheep and Mixed) are used as case study farming systems for this work. Farm data used are land area (arable, grassland and rough grazing land), family labour, production (milk yield, crop yield) and animal numbers (in different age categories such as calf, heifer, dairy etc). The FBS also provided data on revenues and costs of production, farm subsidies, farm fixed costs and total farm CO₂ equivalent methane emissions. This methane emission is converted into emission per livestock unit (LU) and used in the model.

Feed supplements

The four feed supplements analysed in this work are 3NOP, Asparagopsis (seaweed), Nitrate and essential oils. All of these feed supplements are methane inhibitors and have potential to reduce methane emission from livestock farms. Several studies investigated effectiveness, implementation procedure, cost of implementation, effect on feed intake and impact on production (Table 1). The effectiveness of reduce methane emission, however, varies widely in these studies. This work excluded the extreme values of the effects from the literature and used the most common middle ground values. The variation in efficacy range of effectiveness is largely based on animal species, production level, management, environment, and feed regime. In this work, it was assumed that the feed supplements were used on all animals throughout the year so that the cost of the supplements were included in the model as additional expenditure per day per livestock unit.

Table 1: Physical and economic parameters for different feed supplements

Feed supplement	Livestock	Changes (%)			Cost (£/d/lu)	Reference	
		Methane* (range)	Feed intake	Production			
3NOP (Bovaer)	Dairy	-25	-10 to -90	-1	£0.20	Castro Montoya et al (2015); Carrazco et al 2020; Reynold et al., 2014; Hristov et al., 2015, 2020; van Wesemael et al., 2019, Melgar et al., 2020, 2021; van Gatelan et al., 2020; Meale et al., 2021; Haisan et al., 2014; Lopes et al., 2016; Martinex Fernandex et al., 2014	
	Beef	-20		-3			
	Sheep	-20					
Nitrate (SilvAir, Bolifor)	Dairy	-18	-10 to -20	-3	£0.10	allaboutfeed.net; cargill.com; yara.co.uk	
	Beef	-5					
	Sheep	-15					
Essential oil (Agolin, Oregon)	Dairy	-15	-4 to -35	+2	£0.04	Reynold et al (2014); Hristov et al 2015, 2020, van Wesemael et al (2019), Melgar et al (2020, 2021), van Gatelan et al 2020, Meale et al 2021, Haisan et al 2014, Lopes et al 2016; Martinex Fernandex et al 2014; Castro Montoya et al., 2015; Carrazco et al., 2020; Duthie et al., 2022; BSAS, 2024	
	Beef	-7					
	Sheep	-7					
Asparagopsis	Dairy	-45	-20 to -97	-1	£0.50	Wasson et al., 2022; Miller et al., 2023; George et al., 2024; Cowley et al., 2024; Alvarez-Hess, et al., 2024; Kinley et al., 2024; Miller et al., 2023; seastock.com.au	
	Beef	-35					+6
	Sheep	-53					

These four feed supplements used in this work is presented below in greater detail.

3-NOP

The synthetic chemical 3-NOP (3-nitrooxypropenol) is the feed additive with a very high potential to reduce methane emissions in livestock sector. Bovaer® is a commercial 3-NOP product which is available in the EU and UK markets as feed supplement. This feed supplement has been recently approved by the UK government (DSM, 2024). Different studies indicated this feed supplement to reduce enteric methane emission in livestock with a range of -10% up to -90% (Reynold et al., 2014; Hristov et al., 2015, 2020; van Wesemael et al., 2019, Melgar et al., 2020, 2021; van Gatelan et al., 2020; Meale et al., 2021; Haisan et al., 2014; Lopes et al., 2016; Martinex Fernandex et al., 2014; Hegarty et al., 2021). This supplement is considered to reduce milk production up to 3% in dairy (Maigaard, 2024). It also is stated to reduce feed intake by 1% in dairy and 3% in beef (Alemu et al., 2021).

Nitrate

This soluble chemical acts as hydrogen sink in the rumen to prevent methane production. The chemical competes for hydrogen in the rumen which is used by rumen bacteria to produce methane. Nitrate is commercially available as calcium

nitrate like commercially available brands SilvAir^{®1} and Bolifor^{®2}. This supplement is considered to reduce methane emission in the range of 10% to 20%. However, nitrate supplement is also argued to reduce feed intake (by 3%) and overall production by 4% (Wang, et al., 2023).

Essential oil (Agolin, Oregano extract)

Essential oil is plant extract which has been used as taste/sensory feed additive. This has additional benefit of reducing methane inhibitor by changing bacterial activity inside rumen. There are a number of commercially available essential oil such as Agolin^{®3} and Oregano extract. Essential oils are considered to reduce methane emissions in the range of 4% to 35% (Castro Montoya et al., 2015; Flockhart, 2017; Carrazco et al., 2020; Duthie et al., 2022; BSAS, 2024). It is also stated that essential oil as a feed supplement can increase feed intake by 2% and overall production by up to 5% (Hegarty et al., 2021).

Asparagopsis

Asparagopsis (red seaweed species) contains bromoform, a chemical known for reducing methane emission. This supplement has a potential to reduce methane in a range of 9% to 97% in different species of livestock (Hegarty et al., 2021; Wasson et al., 2022; Miller et al., 2023; George et al., 2024; Cowley et al., 2024; Alvarez-Hess, et al., 2024; Kinley et al., 2024). Commercially available Asparagopsis is considered to increase production by 6% (George et al., 2024; Cowley et al., 2024).

Modelling

To model the impact of adopting alternative feed supplements on farm net profit, this work used ScotFarm, a farm level optimising model. ScotFarm is based on farm system analysis and uses linear programming techniques to optimise farm resources (Shrestha, 2022). The model determines farm net profit (ρ) using

¹ <https://www.cargill.com/animal-nutrition/products/silvair>

² <https://www.yara.co.uk/siteassets/animal-nutrition/product-sheets/bolifor-cnfn-product-sheet.pdf>

³ <https://www.alltech.com/agolin>

optimised farm resources based on revenues (p) and costs of production (c) for each of the farm activity (i) for all farms (f).

$$\rho = \sum X_i * (p - c)_i + S - l_i - fd_i - FC \quad \forall f$$

Where, X = farm output; S = total farm subsidies; l = labour costs; fd = feed costs; FC = fixed cost

The model is configured separately under 4 alternative scenarios adding feed supplement implementation cost, changes in feed intake, changes in production (milk yield and live weight) and reduction in methane emission per LU. A schematic diagram of the modelling work plan is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of the modelling work

Economic assessment

The farm net profit which is used as the measuring parameter for the economic assessment. The farm net profit under the alternative feed supplement scenario is compared with a baseline (a status quo condition) to determine the impact of the alternative feed supplement on farm economy.

Cost benefit analysis (CBA)

The CBA is conducted to determine cost effectiveness of alternative supplements. This analysis is based on marginal abatement cost (CB) which is the change in farm profits ($\Delta\rho$) to achieve reduction of a unit of methane emissions (Δe) under each feed supplement scenario.

$$CB = \Delta\rho/\Delta e$$

Where, $\Delta\rho$ includes cost of feed supplement, change in feed cost due to a change in feed intake, change in farm revenue due to a change in production.

Results

Preliminary results of two case studies (dairy and beef farming systems) are presented here. These results are presented here as examples.

Case study 1: Dairy farming system

Economic assessment

Three of the feed supplements (3NOP, Nitrate and Asparagopsis) have similar economic impact on an average dairy farm. They caused a small but negative effect (-2%) on farm net profit (Figure 2). Agolin as a supplement has the least negative impact on farm net profit.

Figure 2: Changes in farm net profit and methane emission on a dairy farming system under different feed supplements compared to the baseline scenario

Figure 2 also presents the extent of methane emission reduction on a dairy farming system. Asparagopsis has been projected to have larger reduction (-22%). All other three feed supplements reduced emissions by 7% to 22%.

Cost benefit analysis

Figure 3 presents the cost (loss in farm net profit) to reduce a kg of CO_{2e} methane emission. Based on this, the essential oil, Agolin, is economically the most feasible feed supplement among the four supplements. It costs only £0.017 to reduce one unit of CO_{2e} methane emission (Figure 3). The costliest emission reduction among the studied four feed supplements for Nitrate which costs £0.09 per kg of CO_{2e} methane emission.

Figure 3: Cost of reducing per kg of CO_{2e} methane emission under four feed supplements

Case study 2: Beef farming system

Economic impact

The economic impact of using feed supplements in beef farming system is higher than dairy farming system. The reduction in farm net profit under four feed supplements ranges from 21% to 25% (Figure 4). Agolin, an essential oil, is projected to have the lowest economic impact on beef farming system whereas 3NOP show the highest negative impact economically on the beef farming system.

Figure 4: Changes in farm net profit and methane emissions on a beef farming system under different feed supplements compared to the baseline scenario

Asparagopsis supplement is projected to reduce larger methane emissions on a beef farming system compared to other three feed supplements (Figure 2). Nitrate and Agolin supplements are estimated to reduce the smallest amount of methane emission (< -5%) in this farming system.

Cost benefit analysis

Costs of implementing the four feed supplements in beef farming system is higher than in dairy farming system. The cost of reducing a unit of CO_{2e} methane emission ranges from £0.04 to £0.30 (Figure 5). Nitrate is projected to be the most cost

effective and Agolin, the least cost-effective feed supplements to be implemented on beef farms.

Figure 5: Cost of reducing 1 kg of CO_{2e} methane emission under 4 feed supplements in the beef farming system

Summary

This technical note presented the methodological concept of economic assessment and cost benefits of feed supplements on livestock farms. This methodology will be extended to include different livestock farming system including the ones that is mixed with arable farming system. The case study results presented here as examples of the output of this work. A final report will be prepared by March, 2025 with updated data and additional livestock farming systems.

References

Alemu, A. W., Pekrul, L. K. D., Shreck, A. L., Booker, C. W., McGinn, S. M., Kindermann, M. and Beauchemin, K. A. 2021. 3-Nitrooxypropanol decreased enteric methane production from growing beef cattle in a commercial feedlot: implications for sustainable beef cattle production. *Frontiers in Animal Science*, 2:641590

Alvarex-hess, P. S., Jacobs, J. L., Kinley, R. D., Roque, B. M., Neachtain, A. S. O., Chandra, S., Russo, V. M. and Williams, S. R. O. 2024. Effects of a range of effective inclusion levels of *Asparagopsis armata* steeped in oil on enteric methane emissions of dairy cows. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 310: 115932

Cowley, F. C., Kinley, R. D., Mackenzie, S. L., Fortes, M. R. S., Palmieri, C., Simanungkalit, G., Almeida, A. K. and Roque, B. M. 2024. Bioactive metabolites of *Asparagopsis* stabilized in canola oil completely suppress methane emissions in beef cattle fed a feedlot diet. *Journal of Animal Science*, 102, skae109

Duthie, C A, Vigors, B., Akaichi, F., Miller, G., Newbold, J. and Eory, V. 2022. Methane inhibiting livestock feed supplements: review of net impacts, barriers to success and consumer acceptance. SRUC

Flockhart, J. F., MacPherson, L., Adamik, C., Hyslop, J and Bell. 2017. The practical feasibility of including lipids and nitrates in livestock diets. *Climate Change*, Scottish Government, Climate Change and Agriculture

George, M. M., Platts, S. V., Berry, B. A., Miller, M. F., Carlock, A. M., Horton, T. M. and Gerge, M. H. 2024. Effect of SeaFeed, a canola oil infused with *Asparaopsis armata*, on methne emissions, animal health, performance and carcass characteristics of Angus feedlot cattle. *Translational Animal Science*, 8 txae 116

Hegarty RS, Cortez Passetti RA, Dittmer KM, Wang Y, Shelton S, Emmet-Booth J, Wollenberg E, McAllister T, Leahy S, Beauchemin K, Gurwick N. 2021. An evaluation of emerging feed additives to reduce methane emissions from livestock. Edition 1. A report coordinated by Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS) and the New Zealand Agricultural Greenhouse Gas Research Centre (NZAGRC) initiative of the Global Research Alliance (GRA).

Maigaard, M. 2024. Combining feed additives to mitigate methane emission and redirect hydrogen in dairy cows. PhD Thesis, Animal and Veterinary Sciences, Aarhus University, Denmark

Miller, G. A., Eory, V., Duthie, C-A., & Newbold, JR. (2023). *Existing and near-to-market methane reducing feed additives and technologies: Evidence of Efficacy, Regulatory Pathways to Market and Mechanisms to Incentivise Adoption.*

Seastock, 2024. Asparagosis seaweed.
<https://www.seastock.com.au/asparagopsis-seaweed/>

SG, 2024. Scottish farm business income – 2022/23.
<https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-farm-business-income-annual-estimates-2022-2023/>

Shrestha, S 2022. ScotFarm – a farm level optimising model.
<https://pure.sruc.ac.uk/en/publications/scotfarm-a-farm-level-optimising-model>

Wang, W., Lund, P., Larsen, M. and Riis Weisbjerg, M. 2023. Effect of nitrate supplementation, dietary protein supply and genetic yield index on performance, methane emission and nitrogen efficiency in dairy cows. J. Dairy Sci. 106:5433–5451

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